

Silvopastoral Dairy System Benefits and Irish Supports

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Dairy cows in an established silvopastoral system, with protected tree in the background

Silvopasture offers Irish dairy farmers a practical way to improve livestock health, soil quality, and farm resilience by integrating trees into grassland land uses. While most dairy cattle graze in open fields, they naturally seek shade and shelter from harsh weather. Historically, cattle thrived in mixed woodlands and pastures, showing the benefits of a more diverse landscape. Setting up a silvopastoral system requires planning. Trees must be protected until mature enough to withstand grazing. Young stock can be introduced earlier using tree shelters, but larger cattle should be restricted until trees are well-established, but the tree-livestock compatibility depends on the livestock and even the breed. Rotational grazing is key to preventing overgrazing, soil compaction, and bark damage, that can be nowadays overcome by using virtual fencing. Fast-growing trees like alder, birch, and willow improve soil by reducing compaction, increasing water infiltration by 60%, and boosting soil organic carbon by 20%. They also help manage wet ground, cutting runoff by 30% and protecting watercourses from pollution. Trees create a better farm microclimate, cooling summer heat and reducing winter chill. This extends the grazing season and improves milk yields, as heat stress can lower production by 10–20%, with cattle burning up to 40% of feed energy just to stay cool. Silvopasture also benefits livestock nutrition. Willow and oak leaves contain tannins that can reduce parasitic loads by 30%, while willow provides natural anti-inflammatories and essential minerals like cobalt. Silage and hay can still be harvested with care between tree rows, ensuring fodder availability and land productivity. Ireland's Forest Type 8 – Agroforestry Scheme supports tree planting alongside dairy farming. Eligible land (0.5+ ha) must have 400+ trees per hectare. Grants include €8,555/ha for establishment and €975/ha annually for 10 years. Land under agroforestry remains eligible for the Basic Income Support for Sustainability (BISS), ensuring farmers retain vital CAP payments while improving land productivity and resilience.

References

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